

What is vocabulary control ?

An organized arrangement of words and phrases used to index content and or to retrieve content through browsing and searching. We use a controlled vocabulary to reduce ambiguity in indexing or describing an entity, whether at the time of creating a record, or of searching . In this process a limited set of terms that have to be used to represent the subject matter of documents. There are two stages of search strategy through which the process of preparing has been done.

The first step involves an analysis of the request to determine what the user is really looking for.

The second step involves translation of the conceptual analysis to the vocabulary of the system.

It may be defined as a list of terms showing their relationships and used to represent the specific subject of the document.

What is the need of controlled vocabulary in IR?

- Control vocabulary helps users to retrieve the relevant document by analyzing the category of user demand and keeping the user categories distinct.
- By using control vocabulary user can get relevant information within a short time.
- Control vocabulary is very helpful in ir because it can determine the personalization features of users easily.
- In the retrieval process various users may use different synonyms or more generic terms to refer to a given concept that's why vocabulary control is used to retrieve information.
- It helps to enhance the indexing method to retrieve or search relevant documents on user choice .
- Sometimes professional words may not be knowledgeable or aware to the user due to searching for any information . by the help of control vocabulary it becomes so accessible to the user.

What are the tools of vocabulary control?

There are several types of controlled vocabularies and related specifications relevant for information.

- Vocabulary control tool
- Simple Term Lists (Pick Lists)
- Thesauri.
- Subject Heading Lists (e.g. LCSH, SLSH)
- Authority Files (e.g. LCNAF)
- Taxonomies.
- Alphanumeric Classification Schemes (e.g., LCC, DDC, UDC)
- Ontologies.
- Folksonomies

What is classaurus?

The classaurus is a tool of vocabulary control. It is developed by Dr. Ganesh Bhattacharyya. It helps to create a structure of a subject and indexing system. It includes the essential feature of conventional alphabetical thesaurus. It is a category based systematic scheme of hierarchical classification. A classaurus can be designed either before starting the indexing work or along with the indexing work.

The classaurus has two parts: the Systematic Part and the Alphabetical Index part.

- The Systematic Part consists of common modifiers. Each entry in the Systematic Part consists of Descriptor; Definition/Scope Note (whenever needed), Synonyms (UF), if any, parts, and species/ types. The hierarchy of terms is shown by indentation indicated by ` (dot). Terms in an array are

arranged according to alphabetical order. Each term in the Systematic Part is assigned a unique alphanumeric code.

- The Alphabetical Index Part to the classaurus contains each and every term including synonyms occurring in the Systematic Part along with its address (i.e. alphanumeric code).

What is the difference between natural language and artificial language?

- Natural language has developed over time with social interaction. On the other hand, Artificial language has been developed with the help of natural language.
- Natural language based on human vocabulary and grammar. Artificial language is based on online and offline databases and also vocabulary.
- Natural language is highly flexible. Artificial language is less flexible.
- Natural language is human based language. Artificial language is Machine based language.
- Natural language can be both a primary and secondary source. Artificial language is always a secondary source.
- Natural language has no limit to its vocabulary and no complete set of rules to describe its syntax and grammar. While in case of artificial language the information to be represented is limited in variability.
- Natural language can be understandable to large groups of users without special training . while in case of artificial language user training in the use of the language is required, the chance of usage errors can be minimized.